
Sustainable Development: An Individual Perspective

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Abstract:

Present paper is conceptual in nature and intent to explore the understanding of society on sustainable development based on brainstorming and observations from the society practices; which are perceived to hinder the sustainable development. The 17 sustainable development goals (SDG) decided by United Nations have been depicted vis-s-vis the initiatives taken by Indian government have also been mentioned. The expected efforts to be done by individual citizens towards sustainability have been proposed. Despite the fact that the government and agencies all over the world are working towards the attainment of sustainable development; ultimately the cooperation and participation of citizens directly and indirectly is going to contribute for the attainment of goals. The article concludes with research questions and hypotheses to facilitate the further empirical research in the domain of sustainable development.

Keywords: *Sustainable Development, Consumerism, Sustainable Development Goals, Eco-System, Sustainable Development and Individual.*

Introduction:

The most popular phrase amongst researchers and in the conferences these days in commerce and management is Sustainable development. A lot of discussions and conceptual researchers have been taking place on sustainable development and the discussions on alternative development business models have been proposed. Majority alternative development models are untested. There finds a need to look into practical implementation aspects of sustainable development at different levels i.e. at the level of central government, state government, local government and at individual level. Sustainable Development is not a buzzword but a word carries value; the word sustainability is life. It is now an oasis in the desert and that desert the human has been creating which in turn is denting the entire eco system. The entire future of life on the earth is depend now on one concept

i.e. Sustainable Development. The prime multiple issues concerning development are; Global warming, Increase in carbon emission and green house gases, Changed weather conditions which has been denting the eco system.

The development is expected to bring happiness to the mankind and all wellbeing of all creators in the eco system but it does not seem happening. Hence, the metric of development needs to be evaluated once. The present metrics of development in the world followed are, percentage increase in GDP, per capita income, per capita consumption, increase in the total economy of the nation, exports trade indicators, foreign reserves, nuclear power, military power, development of urban area, construction and so on. The indicators are moreover economic indicators and are generally accepted as the indicators of development but it is at the cost of destruction of nature and environment which

has been witnessing time and again. The indicators of preservation and conservation of nature and environment are not considered as an indicator of development even though these indicators are appreciated a lot. The world accepts United States of America as a developed nation but not Finland and Bhutan since these nations are topping in happiness index and purely organic states.

The major destruction of nature and environment has happened in last 70 years especially post Second World War period; where the massive industrialization has started taking place and the human and its consequences philosophy of development has caused this destruction. No other creature than human being is responsible for the destruction of environment and nature. The fact of nature's destruction and economic development is that the poor face consequences of destruction made by rich. It is applicable to both with the case of an individual and nation.

Review of Literature:

In 2015 the members of United Nations has adopted 17 goals of sustainable development to comply till 2023. These goals are narrated below along with the actions government of India has taken to comply. NITI Aayog report on SDG India Index 2023-24 has narrated the actions of government of India towards SDG (Bery, 2024)

1. No Poverty: End poverty in all its forms everywhere. The government of India has taken initiative as, Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS), Deen Dayal Antyodaya Yojana (DAY) – National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM), Deen Dayal Antyodaya Yojana (DAY) – National Urban Livelihood Mission (NULM), Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana, Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana, PM Awas Yojana, DDU- Grameen Kaushalya

Yojana, PM Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana and National Social Assistance Programme (NSAP), Atal Pension Yojana.

2. Zero Hunger: End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture. The government of India has taken initiatives like, Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojna / National Food Security Act, 2013, Pradhan Mantri Samman Nidhi (PM – Kisan), National Food Security Mission, PM Poshan Abhiyan, Kisan Credit Card (KCC), PM Kisan Sampada Yojana , PM Fasal Bima Yojna, National Mission of Sustainable Agriculture, Mission for Integrated Development of Horticulture, National Mission for Edible oils- oil Palm (NMEO-OP) National Live Stock Mission, Soil Health Card Scheme, Scheme for Modernization and Reforms through Technology in Public Distribution System (SMART- PDS)

3. Good Health and Well-Being: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages. The government of India has taken initiative as, National Health Mission, Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (Ayushman Bharat), Mission Indradhanush 5.0, Saksham Anganwadi and POSHAN Abhiyan 2.0, Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA), PM Matru Vandana Yojana, PM Jan Aushadhi Scheme, National Ayush Mission (NAM), Pradhanmantri Swasthya Suraksha Yojana, Pradhan Mantri TB Mukta Bharat, Anaemia Mukta Bharat

Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY)

4. Quality Education: Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. The government of India has taken initiative as, Samagra Shiksha, New India Literacy Programme, Mid Day Meal Scheme (PM POSHAN), Pre and Post matric Scholarship schemes for SCs, PM SHRI (School for Rising India), Eklavya Model Residential Schools, Rashtriya Avishkar Abhiyan

(RAA), National Means cum Merit Scholarship, Padhe Bharat Badhe Bharat (PBBB), Skill Strengthening for Industrial value enhancement (STRIVE – EAP), PM Uchcharat shiksha abhiyan (PM- USHA),

5. Gender Equality: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls. The government of India has taken initiative as, Beti Bachao Beti Padhao Scheme, Sukanya Samrudhi Yojna (Girl Child Prosperity Scheme), MUDRA Yojana, Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY), Shakti Sadan, Kastruba Gandhi Balika Vidyalay (KGBV), Pragati Scholarship Scheme for Girls, Women help line Scheme, One Stop Centre Scheme.

6. Clean Water and Sanitation: Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all. The government of India has taken initiative as, Swachh Bharat Mission, Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM), AMRUT 2.0 Scheme, PM Krishi Sinchayee Yojan(PMKSJY), Mission Amrit Sarovar, Jal Shakti Abhiyan- catch the rain, Atal Bhujal Yojana, Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchayee Yojna, National River conservation Programme (NRCP), Namami Gange-Integrated Ganga Conservation Mission, National perspective Plan NPP.

7. Affordable and Clean Energy: Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all. The government of India has taken initiative as, SAUBHAGYA scheme, PM Ujjwala scheme, Unnat Jyoti by affordable LED for all (UJALA), PM- KUSUM Scheme, Rooftop Solar Programme, Green Energy Corridors (GEC), Bio- Energy Programme, National Green Hydrogen Mission, Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gram Jyoti Yojana, National Solar mission, Faster adoption and Manufacturing of Electric Vehicle (FAME) Scheme, PM Surya Ghar Muft Bijli Yojna, Electric Mobility Promotion Scheme (EMPS)

8. Decent Work and Economic Growth: Promote sustained, inclusive and

sustainable economic growth. The government of India has taken initiative as, full and productive employment and decent work for all, Production linked incentives(PLI) scheme, PM Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP), Skill India, Pradhan Mantri Krushal Vikas Yojana(PMMY), National Apprenticeship Promotion Scheme(NAPS), Skill Development Mission, Deendayal Upadhyaya Antyodya Yojana, National Urban Development Mission, Udyami Bharat Scheme

9. Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure: Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation. The government of India has taken initiative as, Digital India, PM Gatishakti – National Master plan for multimodal connectivity, Industrial Corridor Development Programme, National Logistic Policy, North East Industrial Development Scheme (NEIDS), Udyami Bharat Scheme, Bharatmala Project, PM Mega Integrated and Apparel (PM MITRA), Border Area development Programme (BADP) (ACA), Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojna (PMGSY), Make in India / Start Up India, Ease of Doing Business Initiatives.

10. Reduced Inequalities: Reduce inequality within and among countries. The government of India has taken initiative as, Aspirational Districts and Block Programme, Vibrant Village Programme, Pradhan Mantri Vishwakarma Scheme, Umbrella Programme for Development of Minorities, Umbrella Programme for development of Scheduled castes, Scheduled tribe and other vulnerable groups, Scheme for development and other backward classes and Denotified Nomadic and Semi Nomadic Tribes, PM Development initiatives for North East Region, Scheme for Development of Economically Backward Classes (EBCs), Pradhan Mantri Jan Vikas Karyakram (PMJVK)

11. Sustainable Cities and Communities: Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable. The government of India has taken initiative as, Smart Cities Mission, PM e – Bus Seva Scheme, Atal Mission For Rejuvenation, of Urban Transformation (AMRUT), Swachh Bharat Mission – Urban, Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojna – Urban, City Investment to Innovation, Integrate and Sustain 2.0(CITIIS)

12. Responsible Consumption and Production: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns. The government of India has taken initiative as, Lifestyle for Environment (LIFE), National policy on Biofuels, PM – KUSUM Scheme, Renewable energy .Renewable Energy Global Investment Promotion Meet and Expo(RE- INVEST), National Clean India Fund O(NCEF)

13. Climate Action: Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts. The government of India has taken initiative as, National Action Plan on Climate Change, National Mission for Sustaining the Himalayan Ecosystem, National Clean Air Programme,National Mission for Green India, National Solar Mission, National Mission for Enhanced Energy Efficiency, National Water Mission Compensatory Afforestation Fund Management And planning Authority (CAMPA), atinal mission for Sustainable Agriculture, National Cyclone Risk Mitigation Project

14. Life below Water: Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development. The government of India has taken initiative as, Neel Kranti Mission (Blue Revolution), National Plan for Conservation of Aquatic Ecosystem (NPAAE), Pradhan Mantri Matsya Sampada Yojan, Sagarmala Project, Interlinking Of River, National Coastal Mission, Ocean Services, Technologies, Observation Resources Modelling and

Sciences (OSTORMS), Mangrove Initiatives for Shoreline Habitats and Tangible Income

15. Life on Land: Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss. The government of India has taken initiative as, National Afforestation Programme (National Mission for Green India), Intigrated development of wild life Habitats, Project Tiger, Project Elephant, Nagar Van Yojana,National Action Programme to Combat Desertification , National Agroforestry Policy.

16. Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions: Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels. The government of India has taken initiative as, PRAGATI 2.0: Pro – Active Governance and Timely Implementation, Modernisation of Police Forces, RIT (Right to Information Act), Rashtriya Gram Swaraj Abhiyan, Integrated Child Protection Scheme (ICPS), Development of Infrastructure Facilities For Judiciary including Gram Nyayalayas.

17. Partnerships for the Goals: Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development. The government of India has taken initiative as,

The Government of India has initiated aforementioned policies and programs to attend sustainable development goals and their respective state government’s needs to continue and the local government needs to take these policies and programs to the beneficiaries. A bureaucratic system has laid down to percolate the benefits of the programs. Besides this the state and local government needs to take additional programs towards sustainable development suited to the local requirements. The policies and programs supported by individual

citizens and families will conquer the objectives and lead to happy life.

Discussions:

The current quest to attain economic development has raised various issues like, work pressure, tensions, which leads to unhappy life and caused increase in the diseases which leads to increase in the consumption of medicines. The pharmaceutical industry is profoundly reporting their growth; which we term as an indicator of development.

India is striving fast on the track of development. It is on the verge of becoming the third largest economy in the world. Being the number one nation in terms of population the nation is seen as a biggest market by developed nations. Development is needed but not at the cost of destruction hence, in Indian the scenario before thinking on any further development in terms of economy we need to think on basic P's where still India is lagging much behind and these P's are,

1. **Population:** Is mounting and so called said population dividend being the young nation in the world has not seen getting yet. Question arises do our nation has enough resources to comply the basic needs of population?
2. **Poverty:** The rate of poverty is constant since independence and now economists are reporting widening gap between rich and poor one.
3. **Pollution:** The major cities in the nation are arrested with massive air pollution; capital of India Delhi is an example of heavy pollution. Rural India has got soil pollution. Major rivers are polluted and sound pollution found everywhere.
4. **Pure Drinking Water:** Still after 75 years of independence the citizens are away from pure drinking water. Pure and free drinking water at public places is not available. The impure water is inviting many deceases.

5. **Primary Health Care:** Rural India is deprived from the adequate health care facilities. Urban cost of health care is out of reach of common people.

6. **Primary Education:** The targeted gross enrolment ratio speaks on the adequacy of educational system in the nation.

7. **Pure Food:** Government extended the Food security bill and claiming that enough food grains are available but the issue of secured food is on the verge and raised the concern about health.

Sustainable living by Individuals:

The world has witnessed many evolution and revolution by a civilization which has changes the scenario to make it right. In India too such moments from local, state and national level has changed the scenario. The moment by the individuals would be of a great help to attain the sustainable development goals in an effective manner. The social activists and NGOs have already flagged the issues concerning the destruction of nature and environment exhibiting demonstrations like chipko andolan, Narmada Bacho andolan and the like. The major environmental concerns in India are, air pollution, water pollution and water storage, food storage, waste management and loss of biodiversity. Indian is planning to become world's third largest economy on the backdrop of above basic issue. The projected trends seem to be falsifying since the environmental concerns are going to have an impact on the entire eco system which is likely to hinder the economic development. The alternative business models which permits economic development without denting the environment is the only key toward development.

The consumption of individuals i.e. consumer behavior in the market decides the overall consumption and ultimately decides the production and existence of entire supply chain management. The premise is that; the

responsible consumption i.e. consumerism determines the moment in the economy and many of the SDG goals can be attained easily owing the responsible consumerism. (Consumerism is the propensity to consume and keep consuming. It is the drive to buy and own more stuff and to define one's identity through what they own. Economists view consumerism as a positive for consumer spending and GDP growth. Others like psychologists and sociologists, however, see negative effects of rampant consumerism ranging from creating anxiety in individuals to social ills.) The discussion in this section has taken as to the efforts individual as a citizen of this nation, as a responsible consumer can make to contribute towards the sustainable development goals. This premise is against market economy which promotes increase in the consumption of individual and many a times the consumption is unwarranted products and services.

Following discussion is an effort to narrate the efforts individual citizen can initiate to contribute individually towards every sustainable goal decided by United Nations.

1. **No Poverty:** Help people below poverty line to grow in terms of education and earnings.
2. **Zero Hunger:** Avoid food waste at home and outside.
3. **Good Health and Well-Being:** Practice Yoga and Meditation. Take sufficient exercise every day and follow the appropriate diet. Precaution is better than cure.
4. **Quality Education:** Motivate students to take education to enrich skills, knowledge and importantly shape the way to think in right. Present education is moreover exam oriented. The learning of Indian ethos is foremost important.
5. **Gender Equality:** have a benevolent behavior with every human being irrespective of cast and creed.

6. **Clean Water and Sanitation:** Self-discipline regarding sanitation. Do not spit; do not litter on roads, public places. Save water and do not pollute the water bodies.

7. **Affordable and Clean Energy:** save energy should be mission of every house and shift to renewable energy like solar energy.

8. **Decent Work and Economic Growth:**

9. **Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure:** industry to develop sustainable technology, sustainable green products at affordable prices. Develop green infrastructure. Use of natural material in the development of infrastructure. Development of Green houses. Development of supply chain to collect the products after use especially packaging material for recycling or reuse.

10. **Reduced Inequalities:** society is free from caste and creed and we all are human beings.

11. **Sustainable Cities and Communities:** Rainwater harvesting, solar energy Cooperative farming, terrace garden, vertical garden for growing our needed vegetables.

12. **Responsible Consumption and Production:** the citizens should follow the three R's i.e. Reduce (the amount of waste you produce), Reuse (items as much as you can before replacing them) and Recycle (items wherever possible). Here individual can contribute immensely to restrict the consumption which in turn will determine the production of demanded product.

- a. Can we specify the needs and accordingly determine the consumption? So to purchase only adequate.
- b. Can we prefer parching the indigenous products and services?
- c. Can we prefer purchasing the refilling products?
- d. Avoid use and throw culture.
- e. Demand for recycle products.
- f. Demand for organic products
- g. Say no to plastic

- h. Say no to tobacco products, fast food and carbonated beverages.
 - i. Prefer public transportation.
13. **Climate Action:** The collective efforts to reduce the effect of climate change.
14. **Life below Water:** Make use of organic substance to dilute the water pollution.
15. **Life on Land:** be a contributory part of the eco system. Produce no waste. No horns in the cities to compact with sound pollution
16. **Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions:**
17. **Partnerships for the Goals:**

Collective efforts to achieve all SDG:

It is a General saying that, 'Old is Gold' and we need to study era where people were happy and enjoying the life with peace. Till today people with limited expectations and away from material satisfaction seem to be happy (generation baby boomer Born between 1946 and 1964 and **Generation X:** Born between 1965 and 1976). We need to find the root causes of present distractions and need to adopt the era of happiness again with the help of advanced technology. Ministry of education has taken a step towards redesigning the educational system in India remembering the enriched educational system we had those days of Nalanada and Takshashila. The trend of consuming organic products has also on the rise. The adoption of lifestyle has also began changing with yoga and traditional Indian exercise followed by ayurvedic prescriptions. So the reversal trends are witnessing in respective domains and in the days to come the reversal is going to happen to catch hold of happy life.

The entire discussion has reached to set a few questions and to formulate following hypotheses to probe using scientific research design.

Research questions:

1. Government of India has initiated many schemes to attain the sustainable development goals. Many of the schemes are very old. Are all these schemes functioning today? Entire of the schemes are attaining their objectives. Is the beauracracy is held responsible for attainment and non attainment of the goals of respective schemes?
2. Is the state government of Maharashtra is implementing the schemes by central government? Are these schemes attaining the set objectives?
3. Is the self sufficiency and self reliance a prime solution for sustainable development?
4. Does different economic philosophies and sustainable development are related? Is this capitalism distracting sustainable development and socialism supports sustainable development?
5. Does the common person aware of Sustainable development and his role, contributions and expectations in sustainable development?
6. Does the sustainable development efforts are marching towards the more greener, self reliance and technological advanced village.
7. Does the different generations looks sustainable development in the same way? The generations like, X generation, Y generation, Millennium generation, Z generation, Alpha generation and the like.
8. Does the demographic profile and understanding on sustainable development associated?
9. Does the alternative development business models are economically viable and financially feasible?
10. Can we have such economically viable development models?
11. Do we have our science and technology faculty ready to develop the sustainable technology?

Hypotheses:

1. Economic indicators of a nation are positively correlated with carbon and greenhouse gases emission.
2. There is an association with economic systems and indicators of sustainable development.
3. The demographic profile of individual and family are associated with the indicators of sustainable life of individual and family.
4. Consumption of an individual and family are inversely related to indicators of sustainable development.

Conclusion:

The environment destruction of earth can be stopped by the efforts of Government supported by the citizens. The moment of responsible consumerism is likely to attain

sustainable development goals. Micro planning, making awareness on the sustainable development, making accountable and responsible individual citizen is necessary. With respect to every sustainable goal the plans and programs needs to be given to individual for an implementation with the support of local government. The stringent rules and regulations are needed which may dent the indicators of economic development but foster the sustainability. The ultimate goal of every human being is happy life where the earth becomes greener and life in the eco system is enjoying the cause of existence.

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